

VERBAL AND NONVERBAL BARRIERS IN SOCIAL WORK COMMUNICATION

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Abstract:

Both for building a functional relationship between social worker and client, and for the success of the intervention, communication is essential in social work. That is why different verbal and nonverbal communication techniques are used in order to build and maintain efficient relationships between those who communicate in social work and contribute, in this way, to the fulfilment of the proposed objectives of the intervention. However, sometimes communication is disrupted by various factors and obstacles, referred to as communication barriers. These can be both verbal and nonverbal. The more such disruptive factors are in social work communication, the more the outcomes in this field are affected. Therefore, it is recommended that the typical communication barriers are known by social workers in order to avoid them. This paper deals with the most common verbal and nonverbal barriers that can affect communication in social work. In addition to defining and discussing them, various examples from the practice of social work are provided, as well as several suitable recommendations for avoiding them.

Keywords: social work communication, verbal communication barriers, nonverbal communication barriers

1. Introduction

Communication, both verbal and nonverbal, is essential in social work for building a functional relationship between social worker and client, as well as for the success of the intervention. Sometimes, however, communication is disrupted by various factors and obstacles, referred to as communication barriers. These can be both verbal and nonverbal.

Regarding verbal communication, although the words should have clear meanings and what is conveyed or shared between the interlocutors should undoubtedly be understood as such by both parties, there are often some difficulties and problems in the verbal interaction due to various issues, such as the different culture or the social worker's difficulties in adapting to the specific communication style of the assisted person. Some verbal barriers are caused by clumsiness and mistakes made in communication by the social worker, such as the inappropriate use of questioning techniques, expectations and anticipation, presuppositions, excessive moralising, prematurely giving advice and suggesting solutions, judging, criticising, blaming the client, analysing, diagnosing, dramatizing, labelling the client's behaviour, consoling and excusing some client's actions, warning and threatening, attempting to convince the client, by logical argument alone, of the correctness of certain points of view etc.

Alongside verbal barriers, there are also a number of nonverbal barriers to communication (Ștefănescu, 2009). These can impede the good interaction between the professional and the assisted person, although they do not relate to verbal expression, and may be due to issues of place and time, as well as to psycho-physical characteristics of

communication. Such nonverbal barriers are the inappropriate space in which communication takes place, inadequate distance between interlocutors, improper gestures and mimicry of the social worker, unsuitable attire, inappropriate looking and voice of the social worker, etc.

The present paper addresses the most common verbal and nonverbal barriers that can affect communication in social work. The typical verbal and nonverbal barriers are defined and discussed, and different examples from the practice of social work are provided. Moreover, some appropriate ways to avoid them are pointed out.

2. Verbal communication barriers in social work

Verbal communication is essential in social work, because most messages between the client and the social worker are verbal. Although words should have clear meanings and what is transmitted or shared between the interlocutors should undoubtedly be understood as such by both parties, still some obstacles and problems often arise in verbal communication due to various factors, such as the social worker's difficulties in adapting to the specific communication style of the assisted person, or various barriers and impediments in communication. Such factors that may constitute barriers to verbal communication in social work are discussed further in this section of the paper.

2.1 Culture

Culture is one of the factors with a major influence on communication processes. The cultural context can generate different meanings of terms or areas of understanding, which can make it difficult for social workers to communicate effectively with clients and can even create communication gaps between members of multi-personal client-systems (Krogsrud Miley et al., 2006: 202). For example, even a simple question asked by the social worker to the client, such as "What does your family think about this situation?", can create confusion and influence communication, as the term "family" can have different meanings from one culture to another, or even within the same culture, from individual to individual, depending on their cultural affiliation and background, level of education, values and beliefs. Thus, for instance, if the social worker refers in their question to the nuclear family, the interlocutor (the client) may think of the extended family when answering. If these issues are not clarified, communication may be jeopardised because the answer given by the client has a different meaning than the one inferred and retained by the social worker, due to a different understanding of a word used. Such examples are numerous, involving different attributions of meaning to terms and expressions, including those that may seem commonplace and self-evident, as in the example given.

2.2 The presuppositions/assumptions

When "assuming" to understand the content of a client's message, the social worker creates a significant barrier to communication (Compton et al., 2005). The obstacle of assumptions about the meaning of messages occurs when the social worker receives an ambiguous message, controls it insufficiently and believes that the meaning they give it is the correct one. The words themselves can be ambiguous, and the way they are pronounced can lead to unclear thoughts and feelings about the interviewee's behaviour. For instance, the word "intervention" may give different meanings to a social worker, a physician, a policeman or a homeless person. Everyone will tend to think about the meaning of the word in their professional sphere or starting from their own life experiences.

Example: A 16-year-old boy on probation comes to the social worker's office, who invites him to take a seat and asks him how he spent the last week. The boy replies "Good", smiling and looking delightedly at the illustrations in a magazine. The social worker tells him

to leave the magazine, as he is here to talk. Initially she assumed that the boy's smile and gestures suggested his attempt to avoid participating in the conversation. However, the boy's behaviour had another explanation: he did not know how to behave, he had little experience in terms of politeness in human interactions.

Therefore, the social worker must carefully check the meanings or significances of the messages and behaviours, and avoid relying on assumptions about them.

2.3 Expectations and anticipation

Past experiences can generate expectations that filter perceptions of present situations (Krogsrud Miley et al., 2006: 203). Both social workers and clients have expectations about their encounter. Even a simple, well-intentioned message from the social worker such as “we will work together” can be interpreted negatively by the client as a result of their previous disappointments with the “system” (Imber-Black, 1988). Therefore, different prior experiences determine certain expectations, which influence how people transmit, receive and interpret messages. Unverified generalisations and categorisations can distort information and significantly affect the ability to communicate effectively.

Not only clients but also social workers can be influenced by expectations that can be detrimental to optimal communication with the person being assisted. Thus, sometimes the social worker, based on the experience of other cases, may make the mistake of mentally predicting what the client is going to say (Compton et al., 2005). These “predictions” turn out to be even stronger than the client's words or behaviour, distorting the meaning of the messages received. In this way, the response that is anticipated to be received is indeed received, by selecting only the information that confirms the social worker's expectations (Kadushin & Kadushin, 1997).

This barrier, also called “anticipation”, arises because when the interlocutor speaks, the social worker stops listening, because they seem to be sure of what is going to be said and focus only on messages that confirm their expectations (Rodat, 2019). A kind of selective reception occurs. Most of the time, communication is affected by certain diagnostic labels resulting from experience with people facing similar situations. Preconceived notions about the interlocutor emerge, based on the observation of similarities that lead to the development of stereotypes about the type of person one is interacting with. Anticipation occurs to the extent that an existing stereotype is allowed to affect and distort communication. Such stereotypes can develop from one's own experience or from that of an agency.

For example, if a large family, which has been facing various problems for a long time, such as unemployment, alcoholism, domestic violence, etc., again calls on the social work service, the social worker assigned to the case may be tempted, given the history of the family in question, and other similar cases, to consider from the outset the case to be one without solutions, to believe that they know all the facts of the problem anyway, as well as the answers that the family members will give in the interview, which will influence their listening and reception of the meaning of the messages.

Therefore, the social worker must always be aware of the possible influences that may affect them and try not to anticipate what the subject is going to say. In order to counteract the effects of negative expectations, the social worker must listen carefully to all messages and in turn consciously convey messages of acceptance and respect, regardless of the client's situation and the similarity of their case to other cases.

2.4 Excessive moralising

Sometimes the social worker is tempted to moralize, to tell the client what is right and what is wrong, what is good and what is bad, what they have done wrong and how they should proceed further, in the light of the moral norms of the community/society. Although such a

tendency may be well-intentioned, it can be a barrier to communication, as it can result in the client's self-blame, loss of confidence and self-assurance, loss of self-judgement, and dependency. It can also lead to feelings of frustration, guilt, but also anger on the part of the client towards the social worker, and in general towards society and other people, all of whom are perceived as just "lecturing", admonishing, being judgmental, disgruntled and making them feel powerless, worthless or guilty.

However, the goal of the social worker is not to trigger such feelings, but to help the client. Therefore, the social worker should avoid using moralising expressions such as "must/must not", "should/should not/shouldn't", "as is right and proper", "properly/it is proper/it is not proper", etc., as messages that include such expressions can be interpreted with the meaning: "I am telling you what to do because you cannot figure it out".

Examples of excessive moralising to be avoided:

"You should not have done that";

"It is not right to do so";

"You must move out of the house!";

"What will people say if you do this? It is not right and proper to behave like this";

"You should revise your attitude towards your husband!";

"You need to decide sooner what you want to do";

"Others will be upset/ surprised if you act like this/ if you make this decision". Etc.

2.5 Giving premature advice and suggesting solutions

This is a common mistake made especially by newcomers to working with people (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 138). Of course, social work clients seek advice, they need solutions, but such advice and suggestions for solutions given without sufficient assessment of the client's situation can have negative consequences, such as: they can cause fear, resistance and opposition, feelings of inferiority of the client, or it can lead to dependency of the person on the social worker and the social work system.

Even if advice is sought, certain recommendations for solutions, based on superficial information, can trigger negative reactions. The subject may respond: "Yes, but I have already tried... It doesn't work". Although in some cases the temptation for the social worker to intervene quickly is great, this would take place without proper exploration of the problem. However, it is more important for the social worker to lead a process in which the assisted person engages in the discovery of problems and solutions, rather than making suggestions that would increase their degree of dependence (Hepworth et al., 2013).

Examples of premature advice and suggestions of solutions to avoid:

"I think you should approach things differently with your wife. I suggest you...";

"Tell your husband that you do not agree with the way he treats you!";

"I suggest you move somewhere else because you have had so many problems here";

"I think it would be best for you to take a break";

"If your boyfriend is as you say, why don't you leave him and set up a relationship with another boy?";

"I think you shouldn't get a divorce, you don't know what the situation will be like afterwards";

"You should enroll/drop out of college!". Etc.

2.6 Judging, criticising, blaming the client

An attitude of judging, criticising and blaming on the part of social worker also causes a barrier in their communication with the client because, according to a mechanism similar to the one previously described regarding premature advice, it underlines the client's resistance to change. Linguistic formulations that involve blaming and judging the client, especially used in

the context of an insufficiently stable relationship, usually trigger or accentuate feelings of shame, inferiority and/or opposition, leading to self-defensive or even counter-attacking responses from the client.

Examples of wording to avoid:

“This is where you are wrong”;

“Leaving home was a big mistake”;

“You do not think straight”;

“Lying is not allowed!”;

“Your behaviour leaves room for improvement”;

“How could you do such a thing?”.

“One of your problems is that you do not want to look at another point of view”

(Hepworth et al., 2013: 172). Etc.

Responses that evaluate or show disapproval have a negative impact on clients and the process of providing help. They trigger, most often, defensive reactions. Criticism does not often have the desired or intended effects, such as increasing a person's motivation to change. On the contrary, feedback such as an empathic response, which shows understanding of a behaviour, even an inappropriate one in some respects, may be more likely to induce motivation for a more appropriate behaviour (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 139).

2.7 Analysing, diagnosing, dramatizing/theatrical interpretation, labelling the client's behaviour

Formulations that include such aspects rather have the effect of aggravating the symptomatology that the social worker would like to avoid (ibid.). A particular label applied to someone may reinforce the labelled behaviour instead of mitigating it.

Superficial labels and diagnoses represent an oversimplification of complex phenomena, of mental mechanisms, neglecting the uniqueness and individuality of the subject. Certain generalisations do not serve to correctly define problems, nor do they suggest ways to modify behaviour. If the subject accepts certain labels, they may use them as excuses not to get involved. In many cases, it triggers client's resistance. The use of professional jargon in the presence of clients (“neurosis”, “deficiency”, “negativism”, “fixation”, “transference”, “resistance”, “passivity”) also has negative effects, leading to feelings of shame, inferiority, or the idea of a sick person (Hepworth et al., 2013: 174).

Examples of such wording to be avoided:

„You are acting this way/ You behave like this because you are depressed”;

“I notice that you are showing hostility towards your mother-in-law”;

“You are suffering from maladjustment syndrome”;

“You have a disharmonious personality”;

“Your attitude indicates that you are suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)”;

“This is passive-aggressive behaviour”;

“You are really belligerent today”;

“What you are telling me seems borderline subliminal”. Etc.

2.8 “Parroting” client's message, overusing certain phrases or clichés, adolescent jargon, or street language

When social worker “parrots” what the client said, that can be a factor of irritation for the latter. Repeating client's words is not only annoying, but also does not bring anything useful in the communication between the two. Instead of “parroting”, the social worker should use “fresh language that captures the essence of the clients’ messages and places them in sharper perspective” (Hepworth et al., 2013: 178), by applying specific verbal communication and

active listening techniques, such as paraphrasing, verbalization, clarification and reflection, summarising and interpreting, reframing, and so on (Rodat, 2020: 16-21).

Moreover, social workers should avoid superfluous phrases in their speaking, as those are also irritating and have a distracting effect. Using frequently expressions like “you know”, “okay”, “and stuff”, “see/you see”, as well as some “faddish clichés that have permeated today’s language” (Hepworth et al., 2013: 178) (e.g., “cool”, “dude”, “awesome”, “sweet”, “tight”, etc.) is annoying, puts a negative spin on communication, and raises questions about the seriousness and professionalism of the social worker.

Trying to “overrelate” to youthful clients by using adolescent jargon to excess is another mistake made sometimes by social workers (ibid.). The use of teenage slang terms, as well as some street language, makes communication false, inauthentic, impeding the development of an effective working relationship.

Examples of wording and phrases to avoid:

“This is a multi-step process, you know?”;

“Let’s work on this task, okay?”;

“You see, it’s a difficult intervention”;

“I tried to get some information over the phone, and stuff”;

“Your idea is cool”;

“It’s sweet that today you were so punctual”;

“You guys are awesome!”;

“Hey dude, you should know there are rules!”. Etc.

2.9 Consoling and excusing some client's actions

Some wording that attempts to reassure and comfort the person being assisted can be beneficial, instilling hope and leading to the idea that things will get better. However, if they are used inappropriately, by unconditional reassurance of the client that things will get better by themselves or by actions independent of the person being assisted, possibly by suggesting a sense of the client's omnipotence (“you can do anything you want, *if* you want”), they can lead to unfounded hopes and, subsequently, to disappointment if things do not work out (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 140). This is why such an attitude on the part of social workers is dangerous, especially if used indiscriminately. Sometimes such consoling formulations are used by inexperienced professionals who cannot bear the serious personal histories of their clients and rush to console them, to reassure them, in order to reduce the effect of tension. However, it must be kept in mind that certain problems are serious, difficult to solve, or some problems are unsolvable, such as incurable diseases, some disabilities, some mental illnesses, etc. Therefore, social workers have an obligation to listen and learn about the most painful realities for the client, without falling into the temptation to tell them that “it will work out”, “it will be solved”, or “everything will be fine”.

Also, dangerous is the exaggerated attitude of forgiving inappropriate client behaviour, since socially inappropriate behaviours should not be excused, but corrected.

Examples of wording to avoid (Hepworth et al., 2013: 169):

“Don't worry, things will work out”;

“You will feel better tomorrow”;

“I really feel sorry for you!”;

“Everyone has problems”;

“The situation is not as bad as it seems”;

“We all make mistakes”. Etc.

Such formulations on the part of the social worker rather avoid analysing problematic personal histories, as well as exploring feelings of despair, fear, lack of help. Attempting

reassurance prematurely may raise doubts about the authenticity of the social worker's point of view.

2.10 Warning and threatening

Wording that implies warnings, especially in the form of threats, can be serious barriers to communication between the social worker and the client. Indeed, sometimes people receiving care do not consider actions that would be risky for them or others, or that would contravene legal provisions. The social worker must warn them of the potential consequences, but not in the form of threats. The use of wording such as the examples below can trigger disagreement.

Moreover, sometimes clients' verbal behaviour can be aggressive. Even the most experienced social workers can become irritated under the pressure of verbal abuse, accusatory remarks, attacks on their integrity, competence or authority (Hepworth et al., 2013: 175). It is important for social workers to control their own defensive reactions and develop appropriate ways of dealing with negative feelings, and not to respond in the same tone to verbal violence.

Examples of wording that includes threats to avoid:

“If you don't do this way, you'll be sorry”;

“If you could figure out what would be best for you, then you should...”;

“Either you do this, or you won't get any help”;

“We will see who has the power here”;

“From now on, please know... / From now on I will take different measures!”;

“You have no business here under these conditions!”. Etc.

2.11 Attempting to convince the client, by logical argument alone, of the correctness of certain points of view

Such an attitude, embodied in formulations that try to convince the client through various logical arguments, may increase the client's resistance to the proposed change of behaviour, especially in the early phase of the intervention process. For example, it is not enough to explain to an alcoholic client the negative effects of alcohol consumption, or to provide statistics about the consequences of alcoholism. Instead of having the desired effect, such arguments can make the target person feel misunderstood, which will amplify their adjustment difficulties and possible symptoms. Logical arguments sometimes make the client angry and more vehement in their arguments (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 140).

Thus, if the social worker tries to provide “logical” evidence for a change in behaviour, this can trigger hostility and resentment from the client. It is more appropriate to provide information on the basis of which the client can, on their own, examine the advantages and disadvantages of each option.

Examples of wording to avoid:

“Let's see what drug use means”;

“Excessive alcohol consumption eventually leads to serious illness and body collapse”;

“Statistics show that a lot of people die from cirrhosis, a disease caused by drinking”;

“I remind you that you have a responsibility to solve the problem”;

“Think about what you are causing in your family by your behaviour”;

“If you do this, you will get into more trouble”;

“This attitude is going nowhere”.

“In the end, you are still going to leave him. Statistics show that, on average, women leave and return to an abusive relationship by five times before they leave their abusive partner for good”. Etc.

2.12 Using jokes, sarcasm and irony towards the client

In communicating with the person assisted, it is not recommended to use jokes or irony/sarcasm regarding the client or their situation. Although in some contexts jokes may lighten the atmosphere and facilitate further communication, in the case of a relationship with a social work client they are not recommended. Often clients do not understand even the most innocent jokes, which in turn provokes an oppositional reaction. They may feel misunderstood or think they are not taken seriously. Also, sarcasm and irony have no place in a social worker's speech.

Examples of wording to avoid:

“It seems to take quite a few social workers to handle a case like yours”;

“I notice you got up on the wrong side of the bed this morning”;

“I understand that you think you have a problem...”;

“I was thinking of not coming to today's meeting anymore, because maybe you don't have any problems in the meantime!”;

[After the person assisted declares that they did their best to solve their problem]:

“Yeah... I don't doubt that you did...” (in a sarcastic tone);

“You complain so much about your situation, as if you were the only person with problems in the world”. Etc.

2.13 Inappropriate use of the questioning technique

A possible barrier to communication between the social worker and the client may be the inappropriate use of the questioning technique. The art of questioning can be mastered by social workers, who, in time, will learn what questions are appropriate to ask, depending on each client, and also how to ask them. It is important that the questions stimulate responses that can lead to finding alternative solutions and involving clients in solving their own problems.

Recommendations regarding questioning technique:

- starting with the introduction of the interviewer (social worker) to the client (example: “I am Maria Popescu, social worker within...”);
- immediately after the introduction, one should not start with complicated questions, but with “warm-up” questions (e.g., “Did you find our office easily?”; “How are you feeling today?”) and examination questions (e.g., “Tell me more about yourself”);
- avoiding too many close-ended questions, that is, those questions that elicit quick, short answers from the interviewee; while some close-ended questions are necessary or useful (e.g., “What year were you born?”; “What school did you attend?”; “Who are your family members?”, etc.) (Rodat, 2021: 24), others should be avoided (e.g., “Do you like our service?”; “Have you enjoyed our session?” etc.)
- using of open-ended questions, which can elicit more elaborate answers, other than “yes” or “no”; examples: “Tell me more about...”; “What concrete/specific expectations do you have from our organisation?”; “Please explain to me what happened?”; “How did you react when...?”; “Please describe exactly the situation from your point of view”; etc. (Rodat, 2020: 18);
- using questions starting with “who”, “how”, “when”, “which”, “where” (e.g., “Who were the people present when it happened...”; “How did you feel in that situation?”; “Which solutions have you tried?”; “How did you feel then?”; etc.);
- avoiding questions that start with “why” because they can provoke a defensive reaction or even hostility (e.g., “Why didn't you think better before making such an important decision?”);
- avoiding questions that are too long (e.g., “How do you think your husband would behave if in the future you changed your attitude and no longer accepted a subordinate role in the family?”);

- avoiding double or triple questions (e.g., “What are your favourite places to look for a job, who will stay with your children while you work and when you think you can start work?”);
- avoiding multiple questions or *stacking*, i.e., a succession of questions without waiting for answers (e.g., “When you don’t feel you have control of situations, what goes on inside of you? What do you think about? What do you do?”) (Hepworth et al., 2013: 175);
- ensuring neutrality, avoiding questions that suggest answers, that is, *leading questions* (for example, avoiding questions that begin with “Don't you think...?” or “Aren't you...?”, and those that end with “is it/isn't it?”, “do you/don't you?”, “did you/didn't you?”, “would you/wouldn't you?” and so on; e.g., “Aren't you too young to take this step?”; “You only tried to protect your family, didn't you?; “You wouldn't do it the same way the second time, would you?”; etc.);
- avoiding the succession of questions at a too fast pace;
- avoiding the interruption of clients when they are answering;
- using an appropriate tone of voice and carefully monitoring non-verbal communication;
- designing an interview guide in order to avoid possible bottlenecks during the discussion.

3. Nonverbal communication barriers in social work

Along with verbal barriers, there are also a number of nonverbal barriers to communication. These can prevent effective communication between the professional and the assisted person, although they do not relate to verbal expression. Such factors, which constitute obstacles to communication, can be due to issues of place and time, as well as to some psycho-physical characteristics of communication. Among the non-verbal barriers that can affect communication in social work are those listed below.

3.1 Inadequate space

A space that does not allow privacy for communication participants is an inadequate space. Thus, the presence of other people in the same room, the opening of the door, the bustle, the noise in the building, etc. are factors that hinder communication (Krogsrud Miley et al., 2006: 203). Inappropriate furniture can also affect communication. For example, it is totally inappropriate for the social worker to sit behind a desk and the person assisted to sit on a chair, sometimes on a smaller chair than the social worker, or even standing. Such a situation can cause a feeling of inferiority in the person in front of the desk, or even fear and hostility.

Therefore, a position of equality in communication is recommended, suggested also by the non-verbal element of the space: the people discussing should sit facing each other, on chairs of the same size, without a desk between them, and without various obstacles (pieces of furniture, electronic devices, etc.) that prevent them from seeing and hearing each other well (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 137).

3.2 Improper distance between interlocutors

Inappropriate distance between communication partners can also be a barrier. Too much distance can affect the sense of communion, while too little distance can be perceived by the person assisted as an intrusion into private, intimate space, or even as a danger (ibid.).

3.3 Inappropriate gestures and facial expressions of the social worker

These elements of non-verbal communication need to be carefully controlled by the social worker. Thus, gestures and mimicry that may denote inattention, indifference, boredom,

disinterest, lack of understanding, lack of approval, lack of empathy, lack of solicitude, superiority, sarcasm, etc., should be avoided (e.g., lifting eyebrow critically, pursing or biting lips, frozen-on rigid facial expressions, inappropriate smile or laughter, yawning, doodling, scratching the head or other parts of the face and body, picking fingernails, playing with the hair, with a pen or other objects, etc.) (Rodat, 2019: 147). The client's cultural background should also be taken into account and gestures which, in their culture, may possibly be offensive should be avoided.

3.4 Inadequate body posture

When interacting with the client, it is recommended that the social worker keeps their body leaning slightly forward, attentive, but relaxed, not too stiff. Inadequate body posture includes (Hepworth et al., 2013: 168): social worker's body turned at an angle to the client, or leaning back; legs held in improper positions; arms tightly folded; hand or fingers over mouth; social worker squirming or rocking in chair, fidgeting with hands, or nodding head excessively, etc.

3.5 Inappropriate appearance and clothing

The so-called “artefacts” (clothing, shoes, clothing accessories, hairstyle, etc.) can also play a role in communication, that is, in affecting it in a negative way. Usually, people assisted prefer social workers with pleasant appearance and decent attire and footwear, therefore clothes, shoes, clothing accessories and hairstyles that are too extravagant, eccentric, expensive, but also those that are dirty or too humble (which would indicate that the social worker is not able to take care of themselves, so how could they help others?) should be avoided.

3.6 The social worker's inappropriate glance

The eyes play an essential role in communication. However, sometimes the eyes can become an obstacle to communication. An insistent, prolonged stare from the social worker may be perceived by the client as a threat. On the other hand, avoiding eye contact also hinders communication, as it can be interpreted as disinterest and indifference. That is why the social worker should maintain eye contact when interacting with the client, but without staring; moreover, should not stare or fixate an object, look out of the window or at the walls, and should not have an eye level higher or lower than the client's.

3.7 The inappropriate voice of the social worker

The voice can become a hindrance to communication when it is too shrill, or on the contrary, too weak. On the one hand, a shrill voice can be interpreted as a threat or a danger, causing the client to withdraw into themselves and to fear revealing their thoughts and feelings. The same applies if social worker speaks too loudly, give an excessively animated, rapid or staccato speech, clears their throat loudly or consistently, or laughs nervously. On the other hand, a whispering voice of the social worker may cause the client to feel insecure and lose trust in that person. Likewise, if the social worker mumbles or speaks inaudibly, if they are silent often and prolonged, as well as if they have a monotonous voice, that is, if their voice is not modulated to reflect nuances of feeling and emotional tone of client messages (Hepworth et al., 2013: 168).

3.8 Age and gender of social worker, inappropriate for certain clients

In general, it is recommended to assign social workers of the same gender and of an age close to that of the client, since similarities facilitate communication and understanding of the person's problems (Roth & Rebeleanu, 2007: 138). If the age of the social worker is very different from that of the client, this can be a barrier to communication. Moreover, different

genders can sometimes hinder or even block communication, especially when intimate issues of the client are discussed, such as rape or other sexual abuse, domestic violence, etc.

4. Conclusion

In addition to knowledge of effective communication techniques, both verbal and nonverbal, knowledge of possible verbal and nonverbal communication barriers is fundamental to the communication relationship in social work, so that such barriers can be avoided and countered.

In this paper the most common verbal barriers in social work communication were discussed and exemplified, such as expectations and anticipation, presuppositions, excessive moralising, prematurely giving advice and suggesting solutions, judging, criticising, blaming the client, analysing, diagnosing, dramatizing, labelling the client's behaviour, consoling and excusing some client's actions, warning and threatening, the inappropriate use of questioning techniques etc. Furthermore, some usual nonverbal barriers to communication in social work field were pointed out and exemplified, such as inappropriate space and distance, improper gestures and mimicry of the social worker, unsuitable „artefacts” like attire and hairstyles, inappropriate gaze, body posture and voice of the social worker etc.

Only a good knowledge of these verbal and nonverbal barriers may help avoiding obstacles and impediments that can affect effective communication and the good interaction between the social worker and the client, and may contribute to building the relationship based on trust and support, which is the basis of the social work profession, and, in general, to the success of social work interventions.

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